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Short Communication:

A FRAMEWORK FOR COUNTERMEASURES DESIGN TO SUPPORT PROFESSIONAL DRIVERS' FITNESS-TO-DRIVE

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Short title: A framework for fitness-to-drive countermeasure design

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new conceptual framework, and stepwise approach to populate it, for informing countermeasure development to support fitness-to-drive for professional drivers. Professional drivers are vital to the transport network; however, the job is demanding and drivers are vulnerable to impairments which may impact safe driving. Countermeasures are any action or activity that mitigates the impact or frequency of occurrence of driver impairment. The framework proposes countermeasures to be delivered across three time points: Operational (during shift), Tactical (immediately after shift) and Strategic (outside of on-shift) and at multiple system levels, e.g., driver, manager, enforcement etc. The framework was successfully pilot tested with three different professional driver use cases: autonomous shuttles, taxi, and garbage truck drivers. This structured approach to countermeasure design offers potential to improve driver health and enhance road safety. The work was conducted within PANACEA, an EU project, grant agreement number 953426.

Key words: driver health, workplace risk management, systems thinking, road safety, professional drivers, driver impairment.

Professional drivers are at high risk of driving impairment as they may engage in long driving hours and experience work as well as homelife pressures which can influence their fitness-to-drive¹. Fitness-to-drive is a particularly important topic as driving performance decrement is evident in relation to many driver impairment states including those related to alcohol², medication³, stress⁴ and fatigue⁵. Being fit to drive is not always easy to achieve even for the most conscientious of drivers. There may be cases where drivers might not be aware of risks or appropriate mitigation strategies. For example, while alcohol and illicit drugs are clearly not allowed during driving and many drivers will be conscientious and avoid these if they believe that their driving is going to be impacted, they may be less aware of their residual effects⁶. While there is an expectation that individual drivers manage their own health and turn up fit for work it is also a shared responsibility of the employer to support in this endeavour⁷.

The risk of driver impairment can be reduced and managed through effective countermeasures. We define countermeasures as any action or activity that mitigates the impact or frequency of occurrence of driver impairment. The benefit of any particular countermeasure depends on its relevance to the underlying cause of the impairment. Taking an example of fatigue, May and Baldwin⁸ identify three mechanisms through which driving performance decrement may occur: active task related fatigue, passive task related fatigue and sleep related fatigue. Although the manifestation of the driving performance decrement may appear identical, the mechanism for the cause of impairment leading to the decrement becomes important when developing countermeasures. If impairment is caused by sleep-related fatigue, then stopping driving to stretch legs is not going to be beneficial because it does not target the biological drivers of sleepiness. However, if the fatigue is caused by passive task-related fatigue stopping to stretch legs would be beneficial. Understanding the context around driver impairment is a vital step in planning for any countermeasure development⁹.

This paper presents a conceptual framework structuring countermeasure development with a holistic outlook. The potential for its application is evidenced by pilot testing using three commercial driver case studies: autonomous shuttles, taxis, garbage trucks. This work was conducted as part of the

PANACEA project, which has received funding from the EU H2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement number 953426).

In driving theory, Michon's hierarchical model¹⁰ introduced the terminology operational, tactical and strategic, aiming to deconstruct the complex decision-making and behavioral processes that underlie driving according to their respective time constraints. In the model, the operational level represents the most fundamental tasks, referring to the execution of actions required for vehicle operation, such as steering. The tactical level refers to less immediate decisions and adaptations to traffic, such as changing lanes, whereas the highest strategic level involves long-term planning, including destination and route selection. The PANACEA countermeasures conceptual framework, shown in Figure 1, this blank template which can be completed by an end user, includes prompts for the process. Three points of temporal influence are included.

Operational: dealing with the “here and now”. Actions needing to take place in the short-term during the on-shift time when impairment is detected, e.g., in-vehicle alert to the driver.

Tactical: mid-term implementation. Action needed soon after but not during the on-shift period when the impairment is detected, e.g., debrief driver on impairment and consequences.

Strategic: long-term implementation requiring ongoing engagement for prolonged period after the on-shift impairment is detected, aiming at behavioural change, e.g. enacting new policies.

The framework states that countermeasures should be identified from each of the operational, tactical and strategic time points for stakeholders including the driver, employer and enforcement.

<Insert Figure 1 here>

The following stepwise process is used to populate the framework:

Step 1: Impairment. Identify commonly experienced impairments for the target transport mode to focus countermeasure development.

Step 2: Context. Understand what contributing factors result in that impairment occurring within the target population.

Step 3: Evidence. Use academic literature and existing best practice to propose countermeasures that appropriately target the outcome of Step 2. Populate each box in the framework.

Step 4: Feasibility. Evaluate countermeasures most feasible for deployment. Retain those which are not currently feasible to consider for deployment in the future.

Steps 1 and 2 should be informed by discussion with frontline workers.

The PANACEA countermeasures framework was trialled using three transport modes: 1. Autonomous shuttle operatives (i.e., bus drivers who also monitor shuttles as part of their job). 2. Taxi drivers and 3. Garbage truck drivers. Steps 1 and 2 were carried out in parallel using focus groups.

In total, 28 participants (2 female) took part in 6 focus groups with 2 to 6 participants attending each. Two groups for each transport mode. The discussion was semi-structured in that there was a guide outlining the questions to be used but the sequence and level of probing was dynamic to the situation to allow discussion to develop organically. Each group was first presented with a fictional “scenario” of a professional driver working in their industry who was facing situations that may influence their fitness-to-drive. Participants were then prompted to imagine themselves in this fictional situation and guided in discussion about work and home factors that might be impacting fitness-to-drive and what might help the driver to overcome their struggles. Prompts included instructions to think about how they might feel in this situation and what they might do/choices they would make in relation to work.

A list of important problem areas for each transport mode was created. All elements of discussion relating to contributing factors to impairments were considered to generate a list of key findings related to this topic. Results were synthesised across the two groups for each transport mode. Participation in focus groups was voluntary, following informed consent. Ethics approval was granted by Loughborough University Human Ethics subcommittee. The focus groups lasted between 45 and 90 minutes. Discussions were audio recorded with the permission of participants and notes were taken by the researcher/s during the discussions. The focus groups were conducted as

part of the broader work of the PANACEA project, only those elements relevant to the countermeasures framework are considered here.

Step 3 reviewed the literature to identify potential countermeasures which could benefit the identified impairments, where possible for the specific transport mode. Where multiple conflicting countermeasures are identified we advise evaluation based on methodological criteria¹¹.

Step 4. The potential countermeasures were presented to relevant transport providers for prioritisation based on practicality for implementation. Using this co-design outlook it is anticipated that the outcome will be of use to a broad range of stakeholders.

The most likely impairment situations identified for each group as having potential to influence fitness-to-drive were the following:

Shuttle operatives: Alcohol use the previous evening before work, fatigue due to scheduling/work distribution within shift and cognitive underload.

Taxi drivers: Self-management of stress during shift, medication use before shift and cognitive overload during shift.

Garbage truck drivers: lack of awareness of signs of sleepiness, rest time not being effective at reducing stress and fatigue.

For pilot testing purposes, only one target impairment was selected for each transport mode and the deployment targets were limited to driver, employer and enforcement (who inspected for drugs and alcohol). Selection was informed by preference of the transport operator (employer), in real world application all identified impairments should be addressed. Three populated frameworks are presented within Table 1 evidencing the outcome after steps 1, 2 and 3.

< Insert Table 1 here >

The PANACEA countermeasures framework provides contribution to the scientific literature through evidencing an applied instructive process for holistic countermeasure development to manage professional driver impairment. The framework population followed the proposed stepwise

approach and drivers were able to engage in the discussions to inform the important target impairments. The framework specifies the need for countermeasures across three time points defined as operational (during shift), tactical (soon after) and strategic (long term), and consideration of multiple levels of the system. This structured layout guided thinking to ensure a holistic approach to countermeasure design. By providing guidance in this way, the user is forced to consider the wider system, an outlook which is beneficial for road safety¹², without required prior knowledge of systems thinking and complex systems models. The main benefit of systems thinking is that it shifts the focus from changing the behaviour of the individual to addressing the wider system, which has a greater impact on safety¹³. For example, a driver making an error due to a lack of sleep might benefit more from a change in shift patterns to accommodate more sleep than simply being instructed to sleep more. It is hoped that such guided techniques will benefit real-world practice.

In the current work, focus groups were successful at identifying health related impairments which are relevant to driving. This is a useful compliment to crash or incident reports¹⁴ as such sources can underreport impairment. For example, in a study of bus drivers 78% of survey respondents who had previously crashed a bus due to sleepiness reported that their employer would not know this was due to sleepiness¹⁵. Suggesting that incident reports may not be suitable for the identification of all types of impairment. Without trust between employee and employer it is not possible to have open conversations about health-related topics¹⁶. In recognition that these are sensitive topics, the PANACEA approach uses fictional scenarios involving a stereotypical driver in the industry to ground discussion away from any individual. A limitation of the current work is that the effectiveness of this setting has not been evaluated, future work should consider the relative benefits and disbenefits of personal vs hypothetical discussions.

During this pilot testing, step 3 of the process (evidence) was informed by use of academic literature to suggest countermeasures. Understanding of scientific literature present a barrier to wider use of countermeasures. While some efforts exist to provide ready access, such as the European Road Safety

Decision Support System (<https://roadsafety-dss.eu/#>), more should be done by the academic community to facilitate dissemination of academic knowledge.

Impairments to fitness-to-drive are influenced by health-related behaviour. Therefore, strategic countermeasures targeting behaviour change are necessary for reducing the risk of such impairments in the long-term. For example, an alcohol interlock will prevent drunk driving at an operational level, but tackling underlying problem alcohol use requires rehabilitation and long-term change¹⁷. A combination of countermeasure types will likely provide greatest impact. The impairment experienced by any one driver varies over time, therefore, the countermeasures posed will be relevant to different drivers at different times. The system used to deliver the countermeasure would need to regulate the delivery so as to only target those drivers in need at any particular time. Future work within the PANACEA project will consider how best to do this in an inclusive and supportive way.

This work is limited to the context of the three professional driver modes considered. Although effort has been made to engage with diverse professional driver contexts in order to capture a broad range of experience, this also limits the depth of knowledge in relation to any one area and may not be relevant to other transport modes. While the countermeasures have not been empirically tested in this implementation, previous literature suggests suitable alignment with the problem areas. That said, further testing should still be conducted.

An open culture where drivers are encouraged to voice concerns and are not penalized is the ideal environment in which to embed the PANACEA countermeasures framework. Successful safety culture occurs when there is a commitment to safety from both the employer and the employee, with support for employees to experience a sense of control over safety¹⁸.

In conclusion, the holistic approach outlined in the PANACEA project offers a new structured and comprehensive framework for developing countermeasures to support the fitness-to-drive of professional drivers. By focusing on specific impairments and contextual factors within each transport mode, the framework ensures that countermeasures are exhaustive and far reaching. This

approach has potential to benefit road safety through guiding workplace practice within a systems approach while removing the potential knowledge barrier to entry for this way of thinking.

Furthermore, as the transportation landscape evolves with the increasing integration of autonomous vehicles, the insights and methodologies from this framework could be invaluable. The holistic approach ensures that even as vehicles become more automated, the human factors that remain critical to safe operation are effectively managed.

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TABLES and FIGURES

PANACEA countermeasures framework				
Transport mode/industry:				
Target impairment/s:				
Process:		Operational	Tactical	Strategic
1. Impairment	Driver/employee targeted	—	—	—
2. Context	Employer/manager targeted	—	—	—
3. Evidence	Enforcement targeted	—	—	—
4. Feasibility	Additional (e.g. Regulation targeted)	—	—	—

Figure 1. The PANACEA countermeasures framework

PANACEA countermeasures framework				
Transport mode/industry: Autonomous shuttle monitoring				
Target impairment/s: fatigue due to shift work				
Process: 1. Impairment 2. Context 3. Evidence 4. Feasibility		Operational	Tactical	Strategic
	Driver/employee targeted	Fatigue detection in cab alerts. Adequate rest breaks	Rest optimisation advice for fatigue	Lifestyle coaching fatigue
	Employer/manager targeted	Changing drivers when needed	Sleepiness informed scheduling Avoid split shifts	Holistic approach to fatigue and scheduling
	Enforcement targeted	Hours of service (HoS) spot checks	Training for to identify fatigue driving signs	Influence regulatory framework HoS rules.
Transport mode/industry: taxi drivers				
Target impairment/s: medication use				
Process: 1. Impairment 2. Context 3. Evidence 4. Feasibility		Operational	Tactical	Strategic
	Driver/employee targeted	Before shift testing for the presence of medication	Night-time testing and advice	Rehabilitation & healthcare
	Employer/manager targeted	Alerting of driver fitness – driver swapping when needed	Medication awareness discussion tools	Education/campaigns to highlight warning signs for managers
	Enforcement targeted	Roadside testing	Training to identify influenced driving	Influence legal limits and per se laws
Transport mode/industry: garbage truck				
Target impairment/s: stress				
Process: 1. Impairment 2. Context 3. Evidence 4. Feasibility		Operational	Tactical	Strategic
	Driver/employee targeted	Headway management during driving Guided breathing exercises	Advice on self-management of stress	Lifestyle coaching related to stress and cognitive load
	Employer/manager targeted	Provide facilities for rest breaks for stress management	Training for managers on how to identify stress in drivers/when driving	Open culture. Reward system for stress management

Table 1: Populated PANACEA countermeasure framework following steps 1,2 and 3 for autonomous shuttle operatives to target fatigue (top), taxi drivers to target medication use (middle) and garbage truck drivers to target stress (bottom).